

Blockchain's Knowledge Gap

: Jenna Pilgrim^a

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Abstract

Blockchain is now infusing itself into every facet of the economy, and it's happening faster than anyone could have predicted. There is currently a growing knowledge gap between business leaders and big technology companies, which is ever widening as new innovations aim to eclipse the leaders of old paradigms. With the rise of ICOs, the Token Economy, and new governance models for society, how can business leaders keep up? Jenna Pilgrim, Director of Business Development at the Blockchain Research Institute in Toronto, Canada aims to give a lay-of-the-land-style address to help inform the discourse around this emerging technology. The Blockchain Research Institute is conducting the definitive strategic investigation of blockchain applications, use-cases and implementation challenges, aiming to inform business and government leaders of the implications of this technology on business and society

Keywords:

Author biography

: **Jenna Pilgrim** Jenna Pilgrim is the Director of Business Development at the \$multi-million Blockchain Research Institute, which is conducting the definitive investigation of blockchain strategies, opportunities, and implementation challenges and is funded by companies and governments worldwide.

The BRI was founded in March of 2017 by Don Tapscott and Alex Tapscott, coauthors of *Blockchain Revolution: How the Technology Behind Bitcoin is Changing Money, Business, and the World*. Jenna was brought on by the Tapscott Group in 2015 to be the hype-master for *Blockchain Revolution*, which has now become a bestseller in Canada and has been translated into 12 languages.

Jenna holds a BBA in Finance from Trent University is a Certified Bitcoin Professional. Jenna co-founded her first company when she was just 18.

In any spare time, Jenna is a triathlete and road cyclist, stemming from her background in competitive Rowing. Active in her community, Jenna is a steward at CAMH Engage, and sits on the board of the Peterborough Rowing Club

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